

Measurement of General Attitude Toward AI and its Relationship with AI Anxiety, Attitude
Toward Robots and Belief in Human Nature Uniqueness: Polish Adaptation of the ATTARI-12
Questionnaire.

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Abstract

Objective: This study introduces the ATTARI-12-PL, a Polish adaptation of the ATTARI-12 questionnaire designed to measure general attitudes toward artificial intelligence (AI) across cognitive, affective, and behavioral facets. Method: An online sample of 332 participants was used for the psychometric evaluation of the ATTARI-12-PL scale. The internal structure and consistency of the scale were assessed, and the validity of the questionnaire was evaluated through correlation analyses. Results: The ATTARI-12-PL demonstrated a single-factor structure and high internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.94$). Strong negative correlations were found between AI attitude and negative attitude toward interacting with robots, moderate negative correlations with AI anxiety and negative attitude toward robots with human traits, and a mild negative association with belief in human nature uniqueness (BHNU). The scale also showed a strong positive correlation with other AI measurement tool: AIAS-4-PL. Gender was identified as a significant predictor of AI attitude, with men exhibiting a more positive outlook toward AI. Conclusions: The ATTARI-12-PL is a reliable and valid tool for measuring general attitudes toward AI in the Polish population. The scale's strong psychometric properties and significant correlations with related constructs support its use in future research on AI attitudes.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, attitude toward AI, attitude toward robots, AI anxiety, belief in human nature uniqueness, humanoid robots

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Disclosure statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

Informed Consent

All participants provided informed consent prior to their inclusion in the study. The consent process ensured that participants were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Participants were informed that their participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences.

Confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were maintained throughout the study.

Patient Informed Consent Statement: N/A

Ethical Approval

This research study received approval from the Ethics Committee of the Institute of Psychology of the Polish Academy of Sciences (approval reference: 11/IV/2024) and was conducted in full accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Data availability statement

The data supporting the results or analyses presented in this paper are available in the OSF repository at the following link:

https://osf.io/vneyh/?view_only=a6216d7b25aa485ca270af7295611f01

Authorship

Jakub F. Juranek: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Writing – Original Draft

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Measurement of General Attitude Toward AI and its Relationship with AI Anxiety, Attitude Toward Robots, and Belief in Human Nature Uniqueness: Polish Adaptation of the ATTARI-12 Questionnaire.

Since the inception of the term ‘Artificial Intelligence’ (AI) during the Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence in 1956, led by John McCarthy (Chudziak et al., 2022; Kubassova et al., 2021), the associated technology has undergone several decades of both rapid advancement and occasional slowdowns (referred to as ‘AI winters’). These phases have culminated in remarkable achievements and widespread adoption of AI-powered technologies experienced today.

Artificial Intelligence is increasingly integrated into various aspects of modern societies, including education (Chen et al., 2020), transportation (Bharadiya, 2023), healthcare (Secinaro et al., 2021), finance (Jáuregui-Velarde et al., 2024), farming (Holzinger et al., 2024), and science (Xu et al., 2021). Although presenting many capabilities, the current and near-future AI systems are expected to be overshadowed by the emergence of forecasted development of so-called Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) - systems projected to reach human level of intelligence in all fields of intellectual activity and capable of cognitive generalization (McLean et al., 2023). These systems in turn are expected to be quickly surpassed by Artificial Superintelligence (ASI), exceeding human capabilities by large margin (Baum et al., 2017). The pursuit of AGI has a long history, with 45 research projects actively working on its development as early as 2017 (Baum, 2017). The AGI level of AI is widely considered to be achievable before the year 2050, with numerous experts pointing to its possible emergence even before the year 2030 or earlier (Baum et al., 2011).

AI technology brings benefits and risks, of which some have already materialized and other are projected to be encountered in the future. Currently broadly recognized challenges considering AI include algorithmic bias (Kordzadeh & Ghasemaghaei, 2022), safety and malicious use worries (Blauth et al., 2022), copyright issues (Lee et al., 2024) and global job loss concerns (Khogali & Mekid, 2023).

The actual advances and risks associated with AI systems development had been for long time preceded by forecasts and projections present broadly not only in scientific literature but in popular culture, especially in the science-fiction genre. Cave and Dihal (2019; Watts & Bode, 2024) analyzed 300 works of fiction and non-fiction and distinguished four main categories of oppositions (dichotomies) expressed in imaginings of AI, each with a positive pole, called a 'hope' and its opposite, called 'fear'. The first dichotomy is the hope of extended life for humans (hope of 'immortality') accompanied by the fear of losing human identity ('inhumanity'). Another pair of opposites is the hope of life free of work ('ease') with contrasting fear of becoming redundant due to emergence of very capable AI ('obsolescence'). The third hope is rooted in the expectation that AI can extraordinarily fulfil individual's desires ('gratification'), accompanied by the fear of alienation: humans becoming redundant to each other. The last dichotomy is based on the hope of AI offering great power over others ('dominance'), alongside the fear that it will turn against humanity ('uprising'). The authors argue, that regardless of how these recognized, common perceptions of AI possibilities relate to the actual realities of the technology is of less importance, than how these perspectives can actually strongly influence how the real-world AI systems are seen, developed, deployed and regulated.

The theoretical work on perceptions of AI is accompanied by empirical approaches aimed of conceptualizing and measuring the actual attitudes toward AI among people. Attitudes

comprise general assessments of individuals, groups, topics and objects. They play a role in the formation of beliefs (Ajzen, 2001) and shape decisions and behaviors (Glasman & Albarracín, 2006). Attitudes vary in terms of their origin, having affective, cognitive or behavioral grounding (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1977; Ostrom, 1969; Svenningsson et al., 2022), they also vary in the degree of strength - certain attitudes have greater impact and better predict behavior than others. In the assessment of attitude strength, consideration is given to indicators evaluated as more objective or subjective. Objectively, attitude strength is reflected in stability (remaining consistent over time), resistance (withstanding challenges), accessibility (quick recall), and spread (influencing related thoughts and behaviors). Subjective indicators include attitude certainty and its perceived moral basis (Luttrell & Sawicki, 2020). Attitudes are sometimes being assessed as implicit, automatic and unconscious evaluations, but the predominant methods of their measurement rely on people's responses to self-report measures (i.e. questionnaires), which approach is known as explicit attitude measurement (Bohner & Dickel, 2011; Briñol et al., 2019).

Several measures have been developed so far to measure attitudes toward AI. These are the General Attitudes Towards Artificial Intelligence Scale (GAAIS; Schepman & Rodway, 2020), the Attitudes Towards Artificial Intelligence Scale (ATAI; Sindermann et al., 2021), the AI Attitude Scale (AIAS-4; Grassini, 2023) and the ATTARI-12 questionnaire (Stein et al., 2024). These instruments were created to evaluate AI attitude in general. Furthermore, there are scales specifically designed to measure anxiety, concerns, and perceived threats associated with AI or related technology, such as robots and autonomous agents. These comprise the Concerns About Autonomous Technology questionnaire (Stein et al., 2019), the Negative Attitude Toward Robots Scale (NARS; Nomura et al., 2006), the Threats of Artificial Intelligence Scale (TAI; Kieslich et al., 2021) and the AI Anxiety Scale (AIAS; Wang & Wang, 2022). In Polish language

context only the tools associated with negative sides of AI and robotics technology have been available until now. In 2023 Modliński and colleagues created the adaptation of the AIAS AI anxiety scale (AIAS-PL, Modliński et al., 2023), earlier the Negative Attitude Toward Robots Scale has been adapted by Pochwatko and colleagues (NARS-PL; Pochwatko et al., 2015). To address this gap and make available a research tool that assesses the general attitude toward AI, considering both negative and positive area of the attitude spectrum, we decided to translate, research factor structure, validate and make available to Polish research community and international researchers investigating Polish-language participants, the ATTARI-12 questionnaire (Stein et al., 2024).

The ATTARI-12 questionnaire is a 12 item compact measurement scale, designed to address the shortcomings of previous AI attitude assessment tools: the focus on negative impressions and concerns toward AI, subdivision into several factors, size (substantial number of items) and lack of acknowledgement of the tripartite nature of attitudes: the affective, cognitive and behavioral facets (Stein et al., 2024).

This paper aims to investigate the psychometric properties of the Polish version of ATTARI-12 (ATTARI-12-PL) and to uncover the relationships between general AI attitude, AI anxiety, negative attitudes toward robots and belief in human nature uniqueness while testing the adaptation's congruent validity. Furthermore, the work attempts to determine the utility of the ATTARI-12-PL general factor by comparison of its similarity via correlation with general AI attitude measured by AIAS-4-PL, another popular and short, general AI attitude measuring tool created by Grassini (Grassini, 2023) and adapted earlier into Polish by the authors of this work.

The permission for the adaptation of the questionnaire had been obtained from the authors of the original ATTARI-12 measure (Stein et al., 2024). The hypotheses and planned data analysis steps were preregistered at https://aspredicted.org/LKZ_H97.

Method

Ethics statement

The research study received approval from the Ethics Committee (approval number: 11/IV/2024) of the Institute of Psychology of the Polish Academy of Sciences and was conducted in full accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Participants

Sample of initial 494 participants had been recruited using research platforms (Prolific & SW Research “Ankieteo”) and social network adds. From the “Ankieteo” platform originated 328 participants, another 115 were recruited via social network adds, with remaining 51 participants coming from Prolific. In line with preregistered rules for excluding observations, records from participants who failed attention check question or for which any data point was missing, were excluded. The number of excluded participants due to failed attention check, was unexpectedly high, particularly on the “Ankieteo” platform, where it reached rate of 42%. In all, exclusion rate for all reasons (missing data and failed attention check) reached 32.8% of the overall responses gathered pool, leaving the number of participants which answers could be analyzed at N=332. The unexpectedly high number of drop-out data turned the available responses pool below the preregistered threshold of minimum 360 complete data records to proceed with calculation. However, the commonly recommended threshold allowing factor analysis was still exceeded by the number of collected responses, which stands at 300 observations and a minimum ratio of 10:1 responses per questionnaire item/variable (Comrey &

Lee, 2013; Yong & Pearce, 2013). Considering carefully these criteria and recommendations, the decision was made to proceed with analysis of the collected data.

The Prolific participants had been compensated for their participation with the recommended Prolific hourly rate in British Pound, the respondents volunteering participation through remaining networks/platforms were not compensated. The age distribution of participants is depicted in Table 1 and the demographic characteristics of the sample (N=332) are depicted in Table 2.

Measures

ATTARI-12-PL. The Polish adaptation of the ATTARI-12 questionnaire was developed through a multi-step process. Initially, a professional translator translated the original English version into Polish. Subsequently, independent translations were generated using three machine translation tools: Google Translate, DeepL, and Microsoft Copilot. Each item in every version was then back-translated to English using the reverse method. In cases where convergence between all the versions occurred, items were automatically picked to form the Polish questionnaire. For the cases where convergence did not occur, translations of items were chosen with the consultation and advice of Polish language specialist, specialized in teaching Polish as foreign language, having also knowledge of English on C1 level of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), to ensure the translations convey the original meaning.

The original ATTARI-12 questionnaire is a 12 item scale developed in English and German versions by Stein and colleagues (2024) in set of three studies. Half of the items (6) have negative valence and are reverse-coded, meaning that agreeing with the item statement represents negative attitude toward AI, example: “I have strong negative emotions about AI.”.

Each facet of attitude (affective, cognitive, behavioral) is represented by four items, two with positive and two with negative valence. Participants respond using a 5-point answer format (1 – strongly disagree, 5 – strongly agree).

Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale – Polish Version (AIAS-4-PL). The English version of the 4-item version of AIAS-4 (Grassini, 2023) has been translated, adapted and validated successfully in Polish context by the authors of this paper, with the psychometric properties of the scale to be published in another work. This brief scale measures attitude toward AI as one general factor. Responses are gathered using a 10-point scale (1 – strongly disagree to 10 – strongly agree).

The Negative Attitude Towards Robots Scale – Polish Version (NARS-PL) is an adaptation developed by Pochwatko et al., (2015) based on the original Japanese 14-item scale created by Nomura and colleagues (2006). The Polish version consists of 12 items, assessing negative attitudes toward robots across two subscales: NARHT (negative attitudes toward robots with human traits) and NATIR (negative attitude toward interaction with robots). Participants respond using a 7-point scale (1 – strongly disagree, 7 – strongly agree).

Belief in Human Nature Uniqueness Scale (BHNUS). Polish version (Pochwatko et al., 2015) of the scale that assesses the degree to which individuals uphold the idea of human nature as unique to their own group and reject the notion that robots could ever be fundamentally similar to humans. The original scale has been developed by Piçarra (2014). Participants respond on a 7-point scale (1 – totally disagree to 7 – totally agree).

Artificial Intelligence Anxiety Scale – Polish Version (AIAS PL). The Polish adaptation is based on a questionnaire developed by Wang & Wang (2022). The scale comprises 21 items that assess four facets of AI anxiety: learning anxiety, AI configuration anxiety, job replacement

anxiety and the sociotechnical blindness component. The Polish version has been validated by Modliński et al., (2023a). The participants respond to 7-point scale (1 – totally disagree to 7 – totally agree).

Procedure

The study was conducted online using the Google Forms platform. Participants were informed that the study was anonymous and no personal data would be collected. They were assured they could withdraw at any stage without repercussions. After accepting an informed consent form and reading a brief instruction, participants responded to items on the measurement scales. One of the items included was attention check question: “To confirm that you are a real person and not a ‘bot,’ please select ‘strongly agree’ for this item.”. The average time for completion of the responses was below 7 minutes.

Results

Descriptive statistics were acquired for the overall AI attitude score, each attitude facet (affective, cognitive and behavioral) and every single item of the questionnaire. The skewness values obtained (ranging from -0.37 to 0.21), are close to zero, indicating a relatively symmetric distribution. The kurtosis values (-1.25 to -0.62) display flatter, compared to normal, shape, exhibiting a platykurtic distribution. The descriptive statistics acquired are presented in Table 3.

The Cronbach alpha coefficient was employed to assess the reliability of the questionnaire. The entire scale exhibits a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.94, signifying excellent internal consistency among the items.

To assess data suitability for factor analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure and Bartlett’s test of sphericity were used. The KMO value of 0.93 indicates excellent sampling

adequacy, and the significant Bartlett test [$\chi^2(66) = 2974.50, p < 0.001$] supports validity for factor analysis.

The investigation of the factor structure of the scale, as preregistered, has been conducted first with the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). To assess the model fit, a number of fit indices were employed. Comparative Fit Index (CFI) result at 0.84 accompanied by the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) value of 0.80 suggested a room for refinement of the model. A significant result was obtained from the chi-square test for exact fit ($\chi^2(54) = 530.78, p < 0.001$), indicating a parting from a good fitting model. Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) of 0.16 was above the suggested cutoff of 0.06 (Xia & Yang, 2019), and the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) obtained was 0.07.

The fit of the single factor model was unsatisfying, thus an approach utilized by the authors of the original scale, the bifactorial analysis, has been employed. In their work Stein and colleagues (2024) at first tested a general single factor model, with no minor secondary orthogonal multidimensionality, obtaining results similar to those found in this work, concluding the assumption for a single factor not taking into account features such as facets of attitudes was too strong. Therefore, they tested three bifactorial models. First bifactorial model assumed a general factor plus two orthogonal specific factors considering attitude facets: cognitive or affective items. Following Eid and colleagues (2017) work regarding anomalous results in G-factor models, they excluded behavioral facet to consider it as reference. In the second bifactor model, negative wording (valence) of items had been selected as the specific orthogonal factor. Their third, final model included all three specific factors identified in the two previous bifactorial models and was characterized as the best fit. In this work all these three bifactor models had been tested, additionally a model not excluding behavioral facet as reference had

also been tried. The fit indices and parameters obtained for each model, including the initial single factor model had been depicted in Table 4.

In case of this work the best fitting model, that also met the commonly established criteria of good fit, has been the bifactorial model with each of the three attitude facets plus the negative wording of the items considered as specific, orthogonal factors in addition to the common general factor. The CFI for this model is 0.994 and the TLI 0.988. The chi-square test for exact fit returned a result close to insignificance [$\chi^2(36) = 55.192, p = 0.021$]. The RMSEA obtained for this model is below the 0.06 threshold standing at 0.04, with SRMR at 0.021.

In addition to the factor analysis, and in accordance with the preregistration, a Principal Components Analysis (PCA) was conducted. The analysis revealed that the first principal component (PC1) was the dominant factor. The loadings on PC1 were substantial, with the item exhibiting the lowest loading at 0.60 (item 4) and the item with the highest loading at 0.86 (item 11). Overall, all items contributed significantly to PC1. This principal component accounted for 59% of the total variance in the data.

Furthermore, a parallel analysis was conducted, as preregistered, to compare the eigenvalues from the PCA with those from randomly generated data. The results of this parallel analysis supported a single component as the optimal solution, confirming the validity of the PCA findings.

The validity of the questionnaire, as preregistered, was assessed by calculating Pearson correlations with scores from related measures (AIAS-4-PL, NARS-PL, BHNU, and AIAS-PL). Correlations had been calculated for overall scores and subscales for those questionnaires that have subscales. There have been high, positive and significant correlation of overall ATTARI-12-PL score with AIAS-4-PL score ($r = 0.85, p < 0.001$). Correlations with all the other

measurements were significant and negative, as expected. The largest negative correlation was noticed between the AI attitude as measured by ATTARI-12-PL and the negative attitude toward interaction with robots (NATIR) subscale of NARS-PL ($r = -0.72$, $p < 0.001$). This is followed by second largest negative correlation with AI anxiety as measured by AIAS-PL ($r = -0.69$, $p < 0.001$) and its related subscales (AI configuration anxiety: $r = -0.64$; AI learning anxiety: $r = -0.63$; AI job loss anxiety: $r = -0.60$; all at $p < 0.001$ significance level), then negative attitude toward robots with human traits subscale of NARS-PL ($r = -0.56$, $p < 0.001$), AI social blindness factor of AIAS-PL ($r = -0.51$, $p < 0.001$) and least negative correlation with belief in human nature uniqueness ($r = -0.27$, $p < 0.001$). The correlation matrix revealed also a very strong positive correlation of AI anxiety with the NATIR subscale of NARS-PL ($r = 0.80$, $p < 0.001$). The complete correlation matrix is depicted in Table 5.

To uncover the possible relationships between demographic factors and attitudes toward AI, a multiple linear regression model was employed, using age, gender, size of place of residence, and education as predictors. The model's residuals were examined for homoscedasticity and normality, the residuals versus fitted plot suggested the assumption of homoscedasticity was met, with roughly bell-shaped distribution of residuals and points close to the reference line in Q-Q plot indicating normal distribution. The regression model revealed that "Male" gender had a significant positive effect on the attitude score (estimate = 0.340, $p = 0.0021$). Other gender categories and residence types showed no significant effects. The "Doctorate" level of education had a near significant positive effect ($p = 0.0635$). The model's R^2 value is 0.078, indicating it explaining 7.8% of the variance in attitude toward AI. The F-statistic of the model was significant ($p = 0.0058$).

Discussion

The study not only adopted and investigated the psychometric properties of the Polish version of the ATTARI-12 questionnaire but also explored significant associations between the tripartite (affective, behavioral, and cognitive) general AI attitude and attitudes toward humanoid robots, belief in human nature's uniqueness, and fear of AI. This research showed that the general AI attitude had the strongest inverse relationship with the negative attitude toward interacting with robots (NATIR). This negative relationship was even stronger than the negative association between AI attitude scores and AI anxiety (both general and specific types), as well as the negative attitude toward robots with human traits. Relationships in the same direction but to a lesser extent were observed between the aforementioned dimensions and the AIAS-4-PL measure. This result suggests that AI attitude measures can be considered moderate proxies for standpoints toward robots. What is interesting though, is that AI attitude score is only mildly negatively associated with belief in human nature uniqueness. This result can be viewed as showing belief in human nature uniqueness possibly does not involve very strong opposition and negative stance toward general AI, which might come from the fact that AI systems come in much more varieties and AI is a more vague category than the concept of humanoid robots, which additionally directly compete with humans in their appearance. Of course, AI systems and components are technically crucial to building the more advanced humanoid robots; however, AI is already present and embedded in a multitude of commonly, everyday used applications and machines, and the awareness of this among respondents is possibly reflected in the results presented here.

Our results also showed a strong, positive relationship between AI anxiety, as measured by the AIAS-PL, and the NATIR component of the NARS-PL scale. This finding suggests that a

negative attitude toward interacting with robots might be an indicator of AI anxiety, and conversely, AI anxiety could be a strong predictor of reluctance to interact with robots.

This investigation showed also a strong positive relationship of the researched and adapted scale, which itself is quite brief, with very short AI attitude measurement scale which is AIAS-4-PL. This result might be useful for consideration of tools by researchers when briefness and little number of items is crucial. Although ATTARI-12-PL is more elaborate scale, including negative-formulated items and respecting the tripartite character of attitudes, the significant, positive correlation of 0.85 exhibits also high utility of the shorter questionnaire.

The analysis of the Polish version of ATTARI-12 supported the general one-factor structure of the scale with the use of bifactorial model accounting for tripartite attitude type items and negatively formulated items. The one factor solution has also been supported by the Principal Component Analysis calculation, with one component model accounting for 59% of the total variance in the data. The adopted scale showed excellent reliability, with the Cronbach's alpha exceeding the 0.9 mark, indicating strong internal consistency. These psychometric parameters position ATTARI-12-PL as very useful questionnaire in broad research context where AI attitude measurement is desired.

Limitations

There are some limitations to the current study. The fact that the participant sample is not representative is one of them. This non-representativeness poses some challenges to the generalizability of the findings, although the minimal skewness and kurtosis in the data regarding the AI attitude score, suggests that the obtained distribution of scores is fairly symmetrical and close to normal distribution. To mitigate this limitation, future researcher could aim at gathering a representative sample and potentially utilize survey methods beyond the online channels.

Another limitation pertains to the test of validity of the questionnaire, our study did not include any measures to assess discriminant validity, which would demonstrate the lack of correlation between it and unrelated measures.

Finally, the results obtained regarding the relationship of AI attitude and AI anxiety, attitudes toward robots and belief in human nature uniqueness, although insightful, are of only correlational character. It would be beneficial to use the results as starting point to directed investigation that could reveal the casual relationship and potential latent factors that underly and determine both the attitudes toward robots and AI in whole variety of their facets.

Conclusion

The ATTARI-12-PL is a novel, brief and compact tool aiming to quickly and reliably measure AI attitude among people. This kind of comprehensive tool, encompassing negative-worded items and built with respect of the concept of tripartite attitude components in design was not available until now for researchers and psychologists operating within the Polish language research context. Our work exhibits that the Polish adaptation of the scale is reliable and valid and can be a valuable asset for prospect research in a contemporary world characterized by the rapid advancement of artificial intelligence.

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Appendix: A

ATTARI-12-PL

Instrukcja

W poniższym kwestionariuszu jesteśmy zainteresowani Twoim stosunkiem wobec sztucznej inteligencji. Sztuczna inteligencja może wykonywać zadania, które zazwyczaj wymagają ludzkiej inteligencji. Umożliwia maszynom wyczuwanie, działanie, uczenie się i adaptację w autonomiczny, podobny do ludzkiego sposób. Sztuczna inteligencja może być częścią komputera lub platformy internetowej, ale można ją również spotkać w różnych innych urządzeniach, takich jak roboty.

	1 Zdecydowanie się nie zgadzam	2 Nie zgadzam się	3 Ani się zgadzam, ani nie zgadzam	4 Zgadzam się	5 Zdecydowanie się zgadzam
1. Sztuczna inteligencja uczyni ten świat lepszym miejscem.					
2. Mam silne negatywne emocje w stosunku do sztucznej inteligencji.					
3. Chcę korzystać z technologii opartych na sztucznej inteligencji.					
4. Sztuczna inteligencja ma więcej wad niż zalet.					
5. Z niecierpliwością czekam na przyszły rozwój sztucznej inteligencji.					
6. Sztuczna inteligencja oferuje rozwiązania wielu światowych problemów.					
7. Preferuję technologie, które nie zawierają sztucznej inteligencji.					
8. Obawiam się sztucznej inteligencji.					
9. Wybrałbym/wybrałabym raczej technologię ze sztuczną inteligencją niż bez niej.					
10. Sztuczna inteligencja raczej tworzy problemy niż je rozwiązuje.					
11. Kiedy myślę o sztucznej inteligencji, mam głównie pozytywne odczucia.					
12. Raczej unikałbym/unikałabym technologii opartych na sztucznej inteligencji.					

Komponenty: poznawczy (pozycje 1, 4, 6, 10), afektywny (pozycje 2, 5, 8, 11), behawioralny (pozycje 3, 7, 9, 12). Pozycje o negatywnej walencji i odwróconym kodowaniu: 2, 4, 7, 8, 10, 12.

Table 1

Age Distribution of Participants.

	Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max
Age	37.95	34	15.58	18	78

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Table 2

Demographic Characteristics of Participants.

	Count	%
Gender		
Male	118	35.5
Female	209	63.0
Other	4	1.2
Not Declared	1	0.3
Residence		
Rural	63	19.0
Small Town (= < 50 k)	62	18.7
Medium City (= < 500 k)	123	37.0
Large City (> 500 k)	83	25.3
Education		
Primary	7	2.1
Secondary	153	46.1
Tertiary: Bachelor	65	19.6
Tertiary: Masters	98	29.5
Tertiary: Doctorate	9	2.7

Table 3

Descriptive statistics for overall score, three attitude facets and every item of ATTARI-12-PL.

	Mean	Median	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Overall Score	3.10	3.08	0.96	-0.13	-0.62
Behavioral Facet	3.09	3.00	1.13	-0.06	-0.83
Cognitive Facet	3.12	3.25	0.91	-0.11	-0.21
Affective Facet	3.09	3.00	1.09	-0.19	-0.77
Item 1	2.79	3.00	1.19	0.11	-0.75
Item 2	3.34	3.00	1.31	-0.29	-1.05
Item 3	3.32	3.00	1.28	-0.37	-0.91
Item 4	3.08	3.00	1.23	-0.11	-0.84
Item 5	3.10	3.00	1.39	-0.12	-1.25
Item 6	3.37	3.00	1.13	-0.26	-0.63
Item 7	2.98	3.00	1.30	0.07	-1.08
Item 8	2.77	3.00	1.25	0.21	-0.99
Item 9	2.96	3.00	1.28	-0.05	-1.02
Item 10	3.23	3.00	1.13	-0.23	-0.62
Item 11	3.13	3.00	1.20	-0.27	-0.78
Item 12	3.12	3.00	1.30	-0.12	-1.11

Table 4

Goodness of fit for rivaling confirmatory factor models for the ATTARI-12-PL.

Model	Factors	χ^2	df	p	CFI	TFI	RMSEA	SRMR
Single								
	G	530.780	54	> 0.0001	0.839	0.803	0.163	0.073
Bifactor								
	G + wording	296.357	48	> 0.0001	0.916	0.885	0.125	0.045
	G + facets: a + c	413.584	46	> 0.0001	0.876	0.822	0.155	0.065
	G + wording + facets: a + c	150.414	40	> 0.0001	0.963	0.938	0.091	0.036
	G + wording + facets: a + b + c	55.192	36	0.021	0.994	0.988	0.040	0.021

Factors in model: G – general factor; wording – negative item wording factor; facets – tripartite attitude facets: a – affective, b – behavioral, c – cognitive.

Table 5

Correlation matrix of ATTARI-12-PL and its subscales with AIAS-4-PL, NARS-PL subscales, BHNU and AIAS-PL and its subscales.

	ATT-12-PL Score	ATT-12-PL Cogn	ATT-12-PL Aff	ATT-12-PL Behav	AIAS-4-PL Score	NARS-PL NATIR	NARS-PL NARHT	BHNU	AIAS PL Score	AIAS PL Learn	AIAS PL Job	AIAS PL Conf	AIAS PL Blind
ATT-12-PL Score													
ATT-12-PL Cogn	0.89 ***												
ATT-12-PL Aff	0.93 ***	0.75 ***											
ATT-12-PL Behav	0.93 ***	0.75 ***	0.80 ***										
AIAS-4-PL Score	0.85 ***	0.75 ***	0.79 ***	0.80 ***									
NARS-PL NATIR	-0.72 ***	-0.60 ***	-0.69 ***	-0.67 ***	-0.60 ***								
NARS-PL NARHT	-0.56 ***	-0.46 ***	-0.53 ***	-0.55 ***	-0.46 ***	0.71 ***							
BHNU	-0.27 ***	-0.21 ***	-0.20 ***	-0.32 ***	-0.23 ***	0.47 ***	0.49 ***						
AIAS PL Score	-0.69 ***	-0.56 ***	-0.69 ***	-0.64 ***	-0.55 ***	0.80 ***	0.58 ***	0.38 ***					
AIAS PL Learn	-0.63 ***	-0.52 ***	-0.61 ***	-0.61 ***	-0.50 ***	0.73 ***	0.45 ***	0.37 ***	0.89 ***				
AIAS PL Job	-0.60 ***	-0.48 ***	-0.61 ***	-0.54 ***	-0.47 ***	0.68 ***	0.54 ***	0.29 ***	0.88 ***	0.61 ***			
AIAS PL Conf	-0.64 ***	-0.51 ***	-0.64 ***	-0.59 ***	-0.50 ***	0.78 ***	0.58 ***	0.41 ***	0.91 ***	0.77 ***	0.77 ***		
AIAS PL Blind	-0.51 ***	-0.41 ***	-0.54 ***	-0.46 ***	-0.40 ***	0.60 ***	0.53 ***	0.23 ***	0.79 ***	0.52 ***	0.78 ***	0.73 ***	

ATT-12-PL Score – ATTARI-12-PL general score, ATT-12-PL Cogn – ATTARI-12-PL cognitive facet subscale; ATT-12-PL Aff – ATTARI-12-PL affective facet subscale; ATT-12-PL Behav - ATTARI-12-PL behavioral facet subscale; AIAS-4-PL Score; NARS-PL NATIR – NARS-PL Negative Attitude Toward Interaction with Robots subscale; NARS-PL NARHT – NARS-PL Negative Attitude Toward Robots with Human Traits subscale; BHNU – Belief in Human Nature Uniqueness; AIAS PL Score; AIAS PL Learn – learning anxiety subscale; AIAS PL Job – job replacement anxiety subscale; AIAS PL Conf - AI configuration anxiety subscale; AIAS PL Blind – sociotechnical blindness subscale. Significant correlations are marked: *** $p < 0.001$

Table 6

Multiple linear regression model summarizing the relationships between age, gender, the size of the place of residence and education as predictors of ATTARI-12-PL total score.

	Estimate	SE	p	Significance
Intercept	3.1394	0.3869	p < 0.001	***
Age	-0.0058	0.0035	0.1022	
Gender (Reference: Female)				
Male	0.3403	0.1095	0.0021	**
Other	-0.5589	0.4809	0.2460	
Prefer not to say	-1.4186	0.9477	0.1354	
Residence (Reference: Rural)				
Small Town	0.1075	0.1720	0.5324	
Medium City	-0.1060	0.1482	0.4750	
Large City	-0.1003	0.1626	0.5378	
Education (Reference: Primary)				
Secondary	0.0802	0.3622	0.8250	
Tertiary: BA	0.2370	0.3747	0.5275	
Tertiary: MA	0.0216	0.3689	0.9533	
Tertiary: DR	0.8926	0.4795	0.0636	.